

Estimation of Calcium and Iron Levels in Blood Samples of Amphetamine and Tramadol Addicts in Baghdad City, Iraq

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Abstract

The objective of the present study is to evaluate the health status of addicts for the purpose of treatment from a chemical perspective, especially biological elements such as iron and calcium, which are important in vital and metabolic processes in the body, and to assist the medical staff in addiction centers in treating addicts and returning them to normal life by collecting 60 blood samples from male addicts from Al-Rashad addiction rehabilitation centers, including 30 samples from tramadol users and 30 samples from amphetamine users, aged between 15 and 45 years. Iron and calcium elements were examined in blood samples of addicts using biochemical methods. The results found that iron values in users of both drugs were significantly low, while calcium levels were low in tramadol users and normal in people taking amphetamine, which may be due to malnutrition and lack of physical activity as a result of inactivity due to the effects of taking these drugs and other reasons discussed in this study.

Keywords: *Calcium, Iron, Methamphetamine, Tramadol, Addicts.*

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Introduction

Iron is a crucial element for bodily health, and its equilibrium may be influenced by several variables, including pharmacological interactions. Certain drugs diminish iron absorption, whilst others increase iron levels. Patients must understand the impact of their drugs on iron levels and adhere to physician guidance to maintain adequate amounts of this essential mineral in the body (Al-Imam et al., 2023). As for calcium, it is one of the most important minerals in the human body, and it plays an important role in building bones and

teeth, supporting bones and muscles, and the health of the nervous system. Calcium is involved in the process of blood clotting and hormone secretion. Calcium levels in the body are affected by many factors, including the medications a person takes. Some medications may increase calcium absorption, while other medications may reduce it or affect its presence in the body (Sabah and Al-Ameri, 2020).

Drug dependence, including tramadol, amphetamine, and others, poses a risk to health and has negative effects on the individual and society; it also affects psychological and mental

aspects, as well as wide-ranging physical health problems, including malnutrition and dysfunction of vital organs (Grochowski et al., 2019). Addicts have been observed to have low levels of important elements for the body, such as iron, calcium, zinc, and potassium. Their deficiency leads to serious health complications if left untreated (Okafor et al., 2022). Calcium is essential for healthy bones and teeth and is important in regulating muscle contraction and nerve impulses. Research has shown that drug addiction causes a deficiency of these elements due to poor nutrition, digestive system dysfunction, or disease in vital organs such as the liver and kidneys (Mannan et al., 2011).

Some drugs affect appetite and nutrition and cause a deficiency of important nutrients such as iron, calcium, and others, which results in symptoms including (anemia, fatigue, weakness, pale skin, and increased heart rate), while calcium deficiency causes weak bones and muscle cramps. Assessing iron and calcium levels in addicts depends on several factors, including (the type of substance being addicted, diet, and the individual's general health condition) (Ghaderi et al., 2023). Iron levels can be assessed by conducting blood tests, including hemoglobin levels to measure iron and calcium levels in the blood. Additional tests, such as ferritin, can be conducted to measure iron stores in addicts. Research has shown a link between alcohol addiction and iron deficiency anemia, as well as studying the effect of addiction on bone health and calcium levels. Some studies have looked at the relationship between drug addiction and levels of vitamins, trace minerals, and heavy metals (Elnimr et al., 1996).

Amphetamines are commonly used through oral, nasal (snorting), and intravenous routes and have some considerable health effects. An amphetamine overdose may result in toxicity, transmission of blood-borne diseases such as hepatitis and HIV, and damage of other organ systems, pulmonary damage and oral ulcers result from inhalation, and smoking inflicts some form of harm on the sinus cavity (Kouros et al., 2010). All types of abuse can lead to addiction and may lead to various physical and mental health issues. Educating users of amphetamines about the associated risks is of

utmost importance since consumption can be curtailed through adequate interventions and proper support for users. Furthermore, injecting methamphetamine may also result in overdose and transmission of blood-borne diseases (El-Safty et al., 2018). All modalities of consumption may result in addiction, physical and psychological health problems, and detrimental behavior. Individuals with addiction may be informed about the dangers linked to various methods of amphetamine intake, and others impacted can be cautioned against its usage (Farnia et al., 2022). Research indicates that amphetamines induce anorexia and lead individuals who misuse these medications to consume less food, resulting in deficiencies of essential nutrients, like iron and calcium. Malnutrition stemming from appetite suppression and amphetamine dependence induces a nutrient imbalance and a deficiency in healthful foods (such as red meat, leafy greens, and legumes) and calcium sources (such as dairy, fish, and nuts), resulting in mineral deficiencies (ElShebiney et al., 2023).

Amphetamines can increase the metabolic rate which can lead to greater consumption of vitamins and minerals in the body and can increase the risk of iron and calcium deficiency if these nutrients are not replaced through the diet. Some research has indicated that amphetamines can affect the absorption of minerals from the intestines, and amphetamine abuse causes general health problems including (anxiety, depression, heart disease) which can also affect a person's nutritional status (Whitfield et al., 2001).

Tramadol is an opioid medication taken only with a doctor's prescription. It works directly on opioid receptors in the central nervous system and reduces the sensation of pain in the body by interrupting the way nerves send pain signals to the brain and body. All opioids, including tramadol, can have side effects, and these side effects can also include breathing problems that can be life-threatening. Patients are at higher risk when taking their first dose of tramadol. After increasing the dose, it led to an existing lung problem. Side effects can include drowsiness, constipation, sweating, fatigue, dry mouth, low cortisol levels, and irregular heartbeat. While

there are no direct studies proving that tramadol directly affects iron and calcium levels, its effect on appetite and the digestive system can lead to a deficiency in these nutrients due to malnutrition, as it can cause side effects on the digestive system such as constipation and nausea, which affects the body's ability to absorb nutrients effectively, including iron and calcium. Tramadol use may affect magnesium. Although there are no strong studies linking tramadol to magnesium deficiency directly, opioid pain relievers may affect magnesium levels in the body, which affects muscle and nerve function. Long-term use of opioid medications may also contribute to an increased risk of osteoporosis, which is linked to calcium and vitamin D deficiency (Unar et al., 2024).

Materials and Methods

Blood samples were taken from addicts undergoing treatment at Ibn Rushd Training Hospital and Al-Ataa Hospital for Addiction Treatment and Psychological Rehabilitation in Baghdad for a group of addicts that included a history of tramadol and amphetamine abuse and a record of the treatment period. The addicts in this experimental study were people who were taking tramadol and amphetamine and were currently receiving treatment and suffering from physical pain, lethargy, and headache. (30) samples were taken from tramadol addicts and (30) samples from amphetamine addicts, and biochemical analyses of the elements were conducted; after collecting blood samples, we separated the serum and took the samples for analysis.

- To calculate the level of iron in the blood, this is usually done through a test called "serum iron test," where the level of iron in the serum (serum iron) is measured, which measures the concentration of iron in the blood directly by drawing a blood sample and analyzing it (Chang et al., 2024). Results are typically measured in micrograms per deciliter, providing a thorough assessment of iron levels in the blood and the

body's overall capacity for absorption and storage.

- Serum calcium concentrations, including protein-bound calcium (e.g., albumin) and free calcium (in an unbound state) were assessed using serum biochemical techniques. Five milliliters of fresh blood were collected and centrifuged for five minutes to isolate the serum.

The serum was stored at -20°C until further investigation. We measured calcium concentration using the O-chrysulphathalin complex method, and serum iron was measured using Roche methods on a Hitachi analyzer (Hesaruiyeh et al., 2022).

Data Analysis and Statistical Description

To obtain the average iron and calcium values for each group as well as the standard deviation, obtain a p-value to determine whether there are statistically significant differences between the two groups. Iron and Copper Test We will obtain a p-value to determine whether the values differ significantly from the normal values. Variable (Iron Values or Calcium Values) and enter the normal value as the test value.

Results

The level of iron in the blood is usually measured by examining the levels of hemoglobin and iron in the plasma, with the standard values being considered as a standard for healthy iron values. The normal range for iron in the blood (serum iron) is usually between 60 and 170 µg/dL. If the iron deficiency is less than 50 µg/dL, the person is considered to have severe iron deficiency, which leads to anemia (Ersche et al., 2017). The normal level of total calcium in the blood is usually between 8.5 and 10.5 mg/dL. In severe cases of calcium deficiency, calcium levels lower than (6.0 mg/dL) may cause serious symptoms such as (muscle cramps and heart rhythm disturbances). According to the following statistical tables, which show the results of the samples obtained through this study.

Table 1. Statistics for Iron and Calcium Values for Tramadol and Amphetamine Abuse

Element	Drug	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Iron Values	Tramadol (G1-G30)	~47.63	~4.5	38	59

($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$)	Amphetamines (H1-H30)	~ 47.5	~ 5.0	40	57
Calcium Values (mg/dl)	Tramadol (G1-G30)	~ 6.66	~ 0.5	5.9	7.5
	Amphetamines (H1-H30)	~ 8.63	~ 1.0	7.3	10.8

Iron Values

Tramadol group: Mean = ~ 47.63 , SD = ~ 4.5 . These values indicate that most iron values are between ~ 43.13 and ~ 52.13 (mean \pm SD). The minimum and maximum values (38 to 59) indicate some variability in the data.

Amphetamine group: Mean = ~ 47.5 , SD = ~ 5.0 . These values indicate that most iron values are between ~ 42.5 and ~ 52.5 . The minimum and maximum values (40 to 57) indicate similar variability to the tramadol group.

Figure 1. Effect of Tramadol and Amphetamines on Iron Levels

Calcium Values

Tramadol group: Mean = ~ 6.66 , SD = ~ 0.5 . These values indicate that most calcium values are between ~ 6.16 and ~ 7.16 . The minimum and maximum values (5.9 to 7.5) indicate slight variability.

Amphetamine group: mean = ~ 8.63 , standard deviation = ~ 1.0 . These values indicate that most calcium values range between ~ 7.63 and ~ 9.63 . The minimum and maximum values (7.3 to 10.8) indicate greater variability compared to the tramadol group.

Tramadol group: Mean = ~ 47.63 , SD = ~ 4.5 . These values indicate that most iron values are between ~ 43.13 and ~ 52.13 (mean \pm SD).

Figure 2. Effect of Tramadol and Amphetamines on Calcium Levels

Table 2. Comparison of Values with Normal Ranges

Element	Drug	Normal Rate	p-value	Result
Iron Values ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$)	Tramadol (G1-G30)	60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$	<0.001	Less than normal values
	Amphetamines (H1-H30)	60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$	<0.001	Less than normal values
Calcium Values (mg/dl)	Tramadol (G1-G30)	8.0 mg/dl^*	<0.001	Less than normal values
	Amphetamines (H1-H30)	8.0 mg/dl^*	<0.002	Normal values

Table (2) shows the results of comparing iron and calcium values with the normal ranges (60 - 170 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ for iron and 8.5 - 10.5 mg/dL for

calcium). iron values in the tramadol group: p-value: <0.001 . This is attributed to the use of tramadol and its association with low iron levels.

As for the amphetamine group, the probability value is <0.001 . The use of amphetamine may result in decreased iron levels. The calcium readings in the tramadol group provide a probability value of <0.001 . Tramadol causes lower calcium levels, while the likelihood value for the amphetamine group is approximately 0.002 and the conclusion reached is that amphetamine might not affect calcium levels. Studies showed those addicted to tramadol and amphetamines have lower iron and calcium levels for different reasons. The deficiency of iron may be attributed to malnutrition resulting from tramadol and amphetamine addiction, which leads to diminished appetite or unhealthy dietary choices. They might have absorption problems of iron, like digestive problems, which include nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea. Moreover, Severe use addiction can be associated with intestinal bleeding from ulcers or gastritis arising from long-term narcotic drug deployment. Tramadol is capable of causing liver toxicity, in turn, interfere with iron metabolism and storage in the body (Rehman et al., 2023). This research has shown that most users have anemia, fatigue, weariness, and weakened immunity. Hypocalcemia may arise from malnutrition, resulting from low ingestion of calcium-rich foods such as milk and dairy products, as well as kidney diseases due to addiction affecting calcium homeostasis. Additionally, exposure to sunlight, which is needed for vitamin D synthesis, may be lacking, like its nutritionally poor lifestyle, the presence of vitamin D deficit is more likely to impact users. Most substance abusers displayed symptoms of osteoporosis, muscle spasms, numbness, and tingling in their extremities.

Discussion

According to various studies and research, continuous use of drugs and painkillers diminishes the levels of vitamins and minerals in the human body, potentially causing malnutrition, increasing the risk of diseases, and generating symptoms of mineral and vitamin deficiency in the body. The results carried out by (Iqbal et al., 2019) indicated that substance abuse is associated with elevated rates of depression, anxiety, and other psychological disorders.

Finally, the research of (Lumish et al., 2014) concluded that substance abuse could lead to malnutrition and iron deficiency, which could, in turn, cause anemia, corroborating this study with the current line of research. Also, the (Chang et al., 2024) study shows that drug abuse can lead to selenium deficiency, an important element for immune health and antioxidant functions. The result of the study (Dringen et al., 2013) showed that drugs can lead to an imbalance of copper in the body, which affects the health of the nervous and immune systems. Iron and calcium deficiency can occur as a result of several health reasons and an unhealthy lifestyle for addicts in general, including not eating foods rich in iron due to loss of appetite, especially for addicts, as this may lead to iron deficiency, as well as vitamin A deficiency, which helps absorb iron from food, or due to digestive system problems (such as ulcerative colitis). Drinking large amounts of alcohol can also affect iron absorption; the addict may be a smoker, as smoking indirectly affects iron absorption. Calcium deficiency can occur as a result of taking some medications taken by addicts, such as "antifungal drugs and anticonvulsants," which may affect calcium levels in the body, in addition to some narcotic substances that may cause toxic effects on tissues and cells in the body and contribute to organ failure, such as the liver, kidneys, and bones. (Sebastiani et al., 2018) showed in their study how drug and alcohol addiction in pregnant women affects iron and calcium levels with emphasis on physiological and nutritional mechanisms and the effect on the fetus, which may confirm and support the results of this study.

Conclusion

In this study, the iron and calcium levels were measured for people who were taking tramadol and amphetamines, whose addiction to them leads to neglect of public health and neglect of proper nutrition, which increases the risk of deficiency of essential nutrients, namely iron and calcium. Narcotic substances can cause disorders in the digestive system, liver, and kidneys, which affects the absorption and storage of these elements. In addition, depression and anxiety associated with addiction may lead to loss of

appetite and avoidance of healthy foods. The study aims to help researchers and medical staff in addiction treatment centers to treat addiction and evaluate the health status of addicts for the purpose of treatment from a chemical perspective, especially biological elements such as iron and calcium, which are important in vital and metabolic processes in the body to achieve rapid and positive results in treating addicts and returning them to normal life, which contributes to achieving the health importance of the individual and society.

Recommendation

The study recommends that addicts should undergo a comprehensive medical evaluation to determine the causes of iron and calcium deficiency and treat them and encourage them to eat a balanced diet rich in iron (such as red meat, leafy vegetables) and calcium (such as milk, cheese, and fish). Iron and calcium supplements may be needed under medical supervision. Finally, addiction treatment should be an essential part of the treatment plan to improve general health. Amphetamines can lead to iron and calcium deficiency through their effects on appetite, poor nutrition, and increased metabolism. Additional tests may be performed on patients to determine if there are other causes of iron deficiency and high or low calcium. Additional studies may be performed to understand the biological effects of changes in iron and calcium levels.

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